

STAKEHOLDERS' AWARENESS, ACCEPTANCE, AND PERCEPTION OF VISAYAS STATE UNIVERSITY'S VISION, MISSION, GOALS, AND OBJECTIVES

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The Visayas State University (VSU) developed a new strategic plan for 2017 to 2027. This plan adopted a revised vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO). This study was undertaken to assess VSU stakeholders' awareness and acceptance of the university's VMGO after its four years of implementation. A descriptive research method was utilized, and the survey instruments were facilitated online via Google forms to reach all VSU constituents, including the four satellite campuses. This approach was chosen because of the preventive measures associated with the COVID-19 pandemic. Two survey forms with Likert-scale-based questions were designed for two groups of respondents. One is for VSU faculty, staff and, other stakeholders (i.e., alumni, partners, residents of nearby barangays) with 124 responses, and a separate survey form for undergraduate students with 159 responses. The results of the study revealed a high level of awareness and acceptance of VSU VMGO among its stakeholders. Of the two groups, the VSU faculty, staff, and other stakeholders have higher awareness and acceptance levels than the undergraduate students. The leading source of information for the VMGO was the VSU's official website, which is quite likely because of the online mode in the pandemic. The majority of the respondents from both groups perceived the VMGO as inclusive and significantly essential for it to encompass all its stakeholders' welfare, especially the students. To keep stakeholders informed and updated, it is recommended that the mode

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of dissemination of the VMGO be maintained, and explore other strategic measures of information dissemination like translating VMGO into the local dialect, that is, Cebuano, Waray-Waray, or Filipino, to reach a wider audience.

Keywords: institutional direction, strategic plan, state university, vision and mission

1. INTRODUCTION

The vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO) serve as the foundation of an educational institution. Robbins et al. (2003) suggest that VMGO statements serve as a fundamental guide for all institution's relevant academic programs and activities. According to Banganan & Banganan (2006), every institution has a corresponding vision, mission, goals, and objectives to attain efficient and effective management. Institutions and their leaders rely on these statements to launch new programs, services, carry out applied research, sustain and enhance their operations, and build a future capacity for change (Calder, 2014). Papulova (2014) found that an enterprises' vision and mission are significant and important parts of strategic management.

In higher education institutions, the mission determines its purpose and identity, core values, and the purpose of its existence (Arado et al., 2019; Salom & Florendo, 2013). Reflecting the mission and the school's aspiration is the vision. This paints its future perspective. The different strategies and the attainment of definite goals lead the school in attaining the vision. These goals are crafted according to the characteristics of its ideal graduates and their desired impact on society. From the goals, the school identifies strategies that are translated to specifics of the program. Then the different departments determine their programs' objectives and the corresponding outcomes, considering the policies, standards, and guidelines.

The Visayas State University (VSU) formulated its 10-year strategic plan for the period 2017 to 2027 (VSU, 2020). This new strategic plan includes the new and improved vision, mission, goals, and objectives. It envisions becoming a globally competitive university for science, technology, and environmental conservation. Its mission is to develop a highly competitive human resource, cutting-edge scientific knowledge, and innovative technologies for sustainable communities and the environment. It has also revised and set new goals and objectives. The five goals are: (1) sustained excellence in instruction; (2) innovative RDE system and competitive S&T products; (3) adequate and

sustainable resource generation activities; (4) efficient, effective, and client-centered administrative support services; and (5) functional and adequate physical facilities and infrastructure. Its objectives are to (1) strive for excellence in agriculture education for regional and rural development; (2) sharpen its focus on impact programs and projects in instruction, research, and the application of new knowledge for the well-being of the small Visayan farmers and rural families; and (3) build enduring linkages with national and international institutions and agencies for the promotion of relevant instruction, meaningful research, and effective transmission of useful knowledge in the rural communities in the Visayas (VSU, 2020). Guided by these VMGO, the Visayas State University aligns all its activities to fulfill its mandated function to its stakeholders. These stakeholders include faculty and staff, partners, alumni, residents living in the nearby community, and students.

The effectiveness of the VMGO, as believed by Compelio et al. (2015), lies in its structure and dissemination. To be attained, the constituents of an educational institution have to be aware of its VMGO and fully comprehend its implications and importance. This may also be the reason why the AACUP accreditors recommended, particularly to VSU, a regular study on the level of awareness and acceptability of the VMGO to the different stakeholders of the university. It is in this development that this study is conducted. It has been four years since the implementation of the VSU vision, mission, goals, and objectives; hence, it is high time to assess the level of VMGO awareness and acceptance of VSU stakeholders. The study results are needed because it is necessary for continuous improvement in the educational quality of the institution and keep attuned with the challenges of the third millennium. Also, identifying the commonly used platforms for dissemination and communication is essential to the university administrators for policy formulation and implementation.

This study assessed the awareness and acceptance of VSU's stakeholders on its vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO). Specifically, it aimed to (i) describe the socio-demographic characteristics of the faculty and staff, students, alumni, and household head from nearby communities; (ii) determine the extent of awareness and acceptance of stakeholders to VSU'S vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO); and (iii) provide some insights for policy actions towards the aim of making the VMGO useful and relevant to stakeholders of the Visayas State University. The results will contribute to the growing body of literature on the importance of creating well-defined, unambiguous, and properly disseminated VMGO so that stakeholders would understand their underlying meaning and purpose.

2. METHODOLOGY

Primary data was collected online using Google forms. A face-to-face interview was not feasible because of the COVID-19 pandemic. Online data collection has been commonly used during the pandemic (Acob et al., 2021; Serião and Ratilla, 2021). Two (2) online survey forms were created. One survey form was intended for the VSU faculty and staff and the VSU stakeholders, such as alumni, partners, and residents of its nearby communities, while the other survey form was exclusive for undergraduate students. The two google survey forms were pre-tested to 10 respondents. After pre-testing, the questionnaire was revised. The team from the Office of the Director for Quality Assurance (ODQA) and the Office of the President, Visayas State University also suggested and recommended some improvements to the questionnaire.

The online survey was conducted from March 29 to April 5, 2021, and distributed to the stakeholders of Visayas State University (VSU). VSU is a leading state university in the Eastern Visayas region and a three-star university (Austero et al., 2012; QS Star, 2020). The Google survey form link was sent to all VSU constituents via email and IP messenger. This is done to reach respondents in the four (4) satellite campuses of VSU, namely Alang-alang, Isabel, Tolosa, and Villaba. The online survey form for undergraduate students was sent to the presidents of student organizations for dissemination. It was also posted online using the official Facebook page of the Visayas Socio-Economic Research and Data Analytics Center (ViSERDAC) to scout random responses from VSU partners, alumni, and those living in nearby communities.

Before answering the online survey, the respondents were informed that their participation was voluntary and could withdraw from the survey at any part of the questionnaire. Respondents were also informed about the purpose of the study and how the collected information will be processed. Informed consent was secured from the respondents through checking the box before answering the online survey.

To determine stakeholders' extent of awareness and acceptance to VSU'S vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO), the Likert scale-based questions were made. Most state universities and colleges in the Philippines assessing the awareness and acceptance of their VMGO were adopting this type of analysis. In this study, the ordered response options provided were: for awareness, 1-not aware, 2- neutral, 3- aware, and 4-very aware; and for acceptability, 1-not acceptable, 2 – neutral, 3 – acceptable, and 4 - very acceptable.

Descriptive statistics were undertaken to summarize the data using licensed software, Microsoft Excel, and IBM SPSS Statistics v26. Frequency counts, totals, and averages were used in describing the data sets. The results were presented in tabular and graphical forms.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

VSU Faculty, Staff, and Other Stakeholders

The survey for faculty, staff and other stakeholders had a total of 124 respondents. This comprises the VSU faculty and staff, alumni, nearby community residents, and VSU partners. The respondents denoted as “VSU student/employee” pertain to faculty and staff who were simultaneously working and studying MS or Ph.D. degrees in VSU. As indicated in Table 1, the majority of the respondents were VSU faculty (60.5%) followed by administrative staff (24.2%). The residents of nearby communities make up a small percentage of the total number of respondents, only 4% of the total respondents.

Table 1. Composition of the first group of respondents

Variables	n	%	
Respondents surveyed*	VSU Faculty	75	60.5
	VSU Administrative Staff	30	24.2
	VSU Alumni	20	16.1
	VSU Student/Employee	12	9.7
	VSU Research/Extension Staff	9	7.3
	Resident in Nearby Community (within 10km radius)	5	4.0
	Parent of Someone Connected to VSU	4	3.2
	VSU Partners (representatives from industry)	1	0.8
	Job Order employee	1	0.8
Location	VSU-Main - Baybay	88	71.0
	VSU-Tolosa Campus	32	25.8
	VSU-Alangalang Campus	3	2.4
	VSU-Villaba Campus	1	0.8
	Total	124	100

*multiple responses

Most of the respondents were from the VSU-main campus in Baybay City, Leyte (71% of the respondents), and the VSU-Tolosa Campus in Tolosa, Leyte (25.8%). Only a few responses were recorded from the other campuses (Table 1). The majority of the respondents were female (67.7%) (Table 2). Almost half of the respondents were single (49.2%) with an average age of 38 years old. Most of them graduated with a bachelor's degree (47.6%), followed by a master's degree (29.8%) and a doctoral degree (17.7%). They also held regular-permanent positions (48.4%) and regular-temporary positions (17.7%).

Table 2. Profile of the first group respondents

Socio-demographic characteristics		n	%
Sex	Female	84	67.7
	Male	40	32.3
	Total	124	100.0
Civil Status	Single	61	49.2
	Married	55	44.4
	Separated	4	3.2
	Live-in	2	1.6
	Widow/Widower	2	1.6
	Total	124	100.0
Age Range	19 – 25 years old	26	21.0
	26 – 35 years old	40	32.3
	36 – 45 years old	23	18.5
	46 – 55 years old	14	11.3
	56 – 65 years old	21	16.9
Mean = 38 years old			
Educational Attainment	Secondary / Vocational	3	2.4
	Bachelors degree	59	47.6
	Masters	37	29.8
	PhD Candidate	1	0.8
	Doctoral	22	17.7
	Post-Doctoral	2	1.6
	Total	124	100.0
Status of Employment	Regular-Permanent	60	48.4
	Regular-Temporary	22	17.7
	Substitute	10	8.1
	Student	8	6.5
	Part-time	1	0.8
	Total	124	100.0

VSU Undergraduate Students

A total of 159 undergraduate students responded to the survey. Table 3 presents the socio-demographic characteristics of undergraduate students. The majority came from the VSU main campus in Baybay City, Leyte constituting 71.1% of the sample, and 28.9% came from the VSU Alang-alang campus. No students from VSU Isabel, Tolosa, and Villaba responded to the survey. In terms of the academic year, the majority of the respondents were third-year students (39.6%), followed by freshmen (35.2%) and sophomores (20.8%) students. Sixty-nine percent of the respondents were female, and 30.8% were male. The average age was 21 years old. In terms of civil status, almost all the respondents were single (99.40%).

Table 3. Profile of the VSU undergraduate students

Socio-demographic characteristics		n	%
Campus	VSU-Baybay	113	71.1
	VSU-Alang-alang Campus	46	28.9
	Total	159	100.0
Year	First Year	56	35.2
	Second Year	33	20.8
	Third Year	63	39.6
	Fourth Year	5	3.1
	Fifth Year	0	0.0
	Sixth Year	1	0.6
	Seventh Year and beyond	1	0.6
Total	159	100.0	
Sex	Female	110	69.2
	Male	49	30.8
	Total	159	100.0
Age Range	16 – 20 years old	81	50.9
	21 – 25 years old	72	45.3
	26 – 30 years old	3	1.9
	31 – 35 years old	2	1.3
	36 – 41 years old	1	0.6
Mean = 21 years old			
Civil Status	Single	158	99.40
	Married	1	0.60
	Total	159	100.00

Source of Information on VSU VMGO

VSU Faculty, Staff, and Other Stakeholders

The respondents were asked where they had seen or learned the information about the VSU VMGO. The top-most source at which most stakeholders answered was from the VSU official website (www.vsu.edu.ph) 86.3% (Table 4). The second and third responses were from the communication letters (76.6%) and learning guides (74.2%), respectively. These were followed by the VSU social media accounts (63.7%) and posters/leaflets/IEC materials (51.6%). These results imply that these platforms are effective in spreading information about the VSU VMGO. The results of the study are quite similar to the study of Buencillo & Buencillo (2018) and Escolano (2021), except for VSU's top-most source, which is the website. The latter could be attributed to the fact that this study was conducted during the pandemic and the main medium for disseminating information and handling classes is online.

Table 4. Sources of platforms/information where VSU VMGO is seen by VSU faculty, staff, and other stakeholders

Sources*	n	%
VSU Website	107	86.3
VSU Communication Letters	95	76.6
Learning Guides/Syllabus	92	74.2
VSU Social Media accounts	79	63.7
Posters/Leaflets/IEC materials	64	51.6
Programs/Convocations	57	46.0
VSU Annual Report	54	43.5
Meetings/Assemblies	53	42.7
Discussion/Explanation in class	48	38.7
Job Vacancy Publication	33	26.6
New employee induction/Training exercise	26	21.0
Radio	20	16.1
Others**	6	4.8

* multiple responses

** email footer, IP messenger, VSU ID, at the entrance door of the office, computer, and desktop

VSU Undergraduate Students

The onset of COVID 19 facilitated the dissemination of VSU VMGO through the VSU website and the VSU social media accounts. This constituted 86.2% and 72.3%, respectively, of student responses. This was followed by the learning guides (65.4%) and the discussion/explanation in class (57.9%). Except for the VSU website and social media accounts, the responses of the students were quite similar to Buencillo & Buencillo (2018) and Escolano (2021), where their sources of information were mainly from the handbook/learning guides, class orientation, general student orientation, and bulletins/billboards.

Table 5. Sources of platforms/information where VSU VMGO is seen by VSU undergraduate students

Students' sources*	n	%
VSU Website	137	86.2
VSU Social Media accounts	115	72.3
Learning Guides/Syllabus	104	65.4
Discussion/Explanation in Class	92	57.9
Meetings/Assemblies	51	32.1
Posters/Leaflets/IEC materials	49	30.8
Programs/Convocation	46	28.9
VSU Communication Letters	43	27.0
VSU Annual Report	19	11.9
Radio	10	6.3
New employee induction/Training exercise	6	3.8
Facebook	4	2.5
Job Vacancy Publication	2	1.3

* multiple responses

Awareness of the VSU VMGO

Vision and Mission Awareness

Figures 1 & 2 show the level of awareness of VSU faculty, staff & other stakeholders, and the undergraduate students for the VSU vision and mission. As shown in the figures, both groups are very aware of the VSU vision and mission, and both groups showed a very high level of awareness – 70.2% and 67.7%, respectively for the first group and 53.5% & 49.7% for the second group. Comparing both groups, the VSU faculty, staff, and other stakeholders are more

aware of the VSUs vision and mission than undergraduate students. The study of Pelicano & Lacaba (2016) showed the same results. The faculty and staff in their institution were very much aware of the vision and mission than the students. It could be because the faculty and staff are involved in facilitating the VMGO information dissemination through the learning and IEC materials, class discussions, communication letters, bulletins and billboards, and other media of VMGO dissemination.

In addition, it was noted that there were still an ample number of undergraduate students (11.3% and 15.1%, respectively) who ticked neutral in terms of their level of awareness for the VSU vision and mission, with only 2.4% each on the side of the VSU faculty, staff and other stakeholders. More so, 3.1% and 2.5% of undergraduate student-respondents were not aware of the existing vision and mission. Maybe these were the students who did not care to read information not on their liking because the VSU vision and mission are found in their syllabus and at the VSU e-learning platform. This contrasted to the study of Bulfa et al. (2017) for VSU which showed a zero answer under unaware for both faculty and staff and the undergraduate students. However, the study of Bulfa et al. (2017) was conducted during the face-to-face classes while this study was during the pandemic.

Figure 1. Awareness of the VSU Vision

Figure 2. Awareness of the VSU Mission

Goal Awareness

The respondents were also asked regarding their awareness of VSU Goals. As revealed in Table 6, most VSU faculty and staff and other stakeholders indicated to be very aware of goals 1 and 2 (41.9% and 42.7%, respectively). For goals 3 and 4, an equal proportion answered aware and very aware (38.7% for goal 3 and 37.9% for goal 4). Moreover, for goal 5, a higher frequency of respondents indicated to be aware (41.9%) than very aware (35.5%).

On the other hand, most undergraduate students indicated to be aware of goal 1 (40.3%), goal 2 (44%), goal 3 (39.6%), goal 4 (39.6%), and goal 5 (38.4%). This was followed by students who opted to be neutral with regards to VSU goals 1 to 5. Further, it is important to note that the proportion of students who answered "neutral" was higher than students who answered "very aware" of VSU goals. It might be because there were several first-year student respondents. Based on the results of the study of Bulfa et al. (2017), the significant factor affecting awareness of VMGO is educational level. The first-year students are new to the university, so they may still be focusing and adjusting on some other things than the VSU goals.

Table 6. Respondent's awareness of VSU Goals

Awareness of VSU Goals		VSU Faculty and Staff and other stakeholders		VSU undergraduate students	
		n	%	n	%
1. Sustained Excellence in Instruction	1 - Not aware	6	4.8	13	8.2
	2 - Neutral	18	14.5	49	30.8
	3 - Aware	48	38.7	64	40.3
	4 - Very aware	52	41.9	33	20.8
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
2. Innovative RDE System and Competitive S&T Products	1 - Not aware	6	4.8	15	9.4
	2 - Neutral	18	14.5	45	28.3
	3 - Aware	47	37.9	70	44.0
	4 - Very aware	53	42.7	29	18.2
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
3. Adequate and Sustainable Resource Generation Activities	1 - Not aware	6	4.8	15	9.4
	2 - Neutral	22	17.7	51	32.1
	3 - Aware	48	38.7	63	39.6
	4 - Very aware	48	38.7	30	18.9
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
4. Efficient, Effective and Client-Centered Administrative Support Services	1 - Not aware	7	5.6	17	10.7
	2 - Neutral	23	18.5	46	28.9
	3 - Aware	47	37.9	63	39.6
	4 - Very aware	47	37.9	33	20.8
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
5. Functional and Adequate Physical Facilities and Infrastructure.	1 - Not aware	6	4.8	21	13.2
	2 - Neutral	22	17.7	45	28.3
	3 - Aware	52	41.9	61	38.4
	4 - Very aware	44	35.5	32	20.1
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0

Objectives Awareness

In terms of respondents' awareness of VSU's three (3) objectives, Table 7 revealed that the majority of VSU faculty and staff and other stakeholders were very aware of objectives 1 (44.4%) and 3 (39.5%). Only 38.7% were very aware of objective 2. However, this proportion is higher than that of the VSU undergraduate students. For the undergraduate students, the majority indicated to be just aware of the three objectives followed by being neutral. Only a few students (more or less 22%) answered very aware of VSU objectives. The results

are related to the goal awareness that is affected by the educational level of the respondents.

Table 7. Awareness of the VSU Objectives

Awareness of VSU Objectives		VSU faculty and staff and other stakeholders		VSU undergraduate students	
		n	%	n	%
1. To strive for excellence in agriculture education for regional and rural development.	1 - Not aware	3	2.4	13	8.2
	2 - Neutral	22	17.7	44	27.7
	3 - Aware	44	35.5	67	42.1
	4 - Very aware	55	44.4	35	22.0
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
2. To sharpen its focus on impact programs and projects in instruction, research, and the application of new knowledge.	1 - Not aware	5	4.0	16	10.1
	2 - Neutral	21	16.9	45	28.3
	3 - Aware	50	40.3	62	39.0
	4 - Very aware	48	38.7	36	22.6
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
3. To build enduring linkages with national and international institutions and agencies.	1 - Not aware	5	4.0	20	12.6
	2 - Neutral	22	17.7	45	28.3
	3 - Aware	48	38.7	62	39.0
	4 - Very aware	49	39.5	32	20.1
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0

Acceptance of the VSU VMGO

Figures 3 and 4 show the results for the acceptance of the VSU vision and mission. Combining the answer for acceptable and very acceptable, 95% & 97% of the faculty and staff and other stakeholders, and 90% & 89% of the undergraduate students expressed their favorable answers.

Figure 3. Respondents' acceptance of VSU Vision

Figure 4. Respondents' acceptance of VSU Mission

For the VSU goals and objectives, most of the VSU faculty and staff, and other stakeholders have a high level of acceptance ranging from 87-93% across the five goals of VSU (Table 8). For the undergraduate students, the acceptance is relatively lower than that of the faculty and staff, and other stakeholders but is still generally high at a range of 78-83%. Nevertheless, 13-19% of the undergraduate students are neutral on the acceptance of the VSU goals. Six students answered not acceptable. This may be because most respondents were still in their first year in college, and understanding the goal statement might be difficult for them.

Table 8. Respondents' acceptance of VSU Goals

Acceptance of VSU Goals		VSU faculty and staff and other stakeholders		VSU undergraduate students	
		n	%	n	%
Sustained Excellence in Instruction	1 - Not acceptable	0	0	5	3.1
	2 - Neutral	9	7.3	30	18.9
	3 - Acceptable	39	31.5	60	37.7
	4 - Very acceptable	76	61.3	64	40.3
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
Innovative RDE System and Competitive S&T Products	1 - Not acceptable	1	0.8	6	3.8
	2 - Neutral	9	7.3	25	15.7
	3 - Acceptable	40	32.3	71	44.7
	4 - Very acceptable	74	59.7	57	35.8
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
Adequate and Sustainable Resource Generation Activities	1 - Not acceptable	1	0.8	6	3.8
	2 - Neutral	15	12.1	21	13.2
	3 - Acceptable	34	27.4	67	42.1
	4 - Very acceptable	74	59.7	65	40.9
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
Efficient, Effective and Client-Centered Administrative Support Services	1 - Not acceptable	1	0.8	5	3.1
	2 - Neutral	14	11.3	28	17.6
	3 - Acceptable	36	29.0	61	38.4
	4 - Very acceptable	73	58.9	65	40.9
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
Functional and Adequate Physical Facilities and Infrastructure	1 - Not acceptable	1	0.8	6	3.8
	2 - Neutral	15	12.1	22	13.8
	3 - Acceptable	36	29.0	63	39.6
	4 - Very acceptable	72	58.1	68	42.8
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0

For the VSU objectives, a high level of acceptance for both groups was noted. (Table 9). Combining the acceptable and very acceptable, 90-94% of VSU faculty and staff and other stakeholders were noted. For VSU undergraduate students, the proportion of those who accepted the objectives was 85-87%. The general results imply that respondents have a high level of acceptance of the VSU VMGO.

Table 9. Respondents' acceptance of VSU Objectives

Acceptance of VSU Objectives		VSU faculty and staff and other stakeholders		VSU undergraduate students	
		n	%	n	%
To strive for excellence in agriculture education for regional and rural development.	1 - Not acceptable	0	0	4	2.5
	2 - Neutral	13	10.5	19	11.9
	3 - Acceptable	36	29.0	59	37.1
	4 - Very acceptable	75	60.5	77	48.4
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
To sharpen its focus on impact programs and projects in instruction, research, and the application of new knowledge.	1 - Not acceptable	0	0	3	1.9
	2 - Neutral	10	8.1	17	10.7
	3 - Acceptable	31	25.0	63	39.6
	4 - Very acceptable	83	66.9	76	47.8
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0
To build enduring linkages with national and international institutions and agencies.	1 - Not acceptable	0	0	4	2.5
	2 - Neutral	8	6.5	20	12.6
	3 - Acceptable	32	25.8	55	34.6
	4 - Very acceptable	84	67.7	80	50.3
	Total	124	100.0	159	100.0

Familiarization of the VSU VMGO through Memorization

The respondents were also asked if they memorized the vision, mission, goals, and objectives of VSU. The memorization of VSU VMGO is an idea added to this study based on the various recommendations of the researchers from various colleges and universities working on the awareness and acceptability of the institutions VMGO (for example, Gracia et al., 2021; Constantino et al., 2020; Estrada, 2018). They recommended the widest dissemination of the VMGO using various media, including a mandatory recitation of the university vision and

mission in the flag ceremony. Figures 5 and 6 revealed the results. For the VSU vision and mission, there were more than half of the respondents (i.e., 53.2% for faculty and staff and other stakeholders, and 50.9% for undergraduate students) partially memorized the vision and mission, and around 36% and 38% of faculty and staff, and undergraduate students, had fully memorized it. A few of them, however, with 11.3% for each group, did not memorize the VSU vision and mission.

In the case of the goals and objectives, there was a great decrease in the number on the side of the faculty and staff and other stakeholders (only 8.10%) who fully memorized. There were 38.7% of them that never memorize. The possible reason might be the length of the phrases to be memorized. The vision and mission are much shorter than the goals and objectives of the university.

Concerning memorization of VSU VMGO, a higher percentage would come from the students because some of the professors were giving incentives like bonus scores during examinations or upon the start of the classes for students who can memorize the VMGO.

Figure 5. Respondents' memorization of the VSU Vision and Mission

Figure 6. Respondents' memorization of the VSU Goals and Objectives

Perception of respondents to VSU VMGO

This section discusses the perception of respondents to VSU VMGO if they agree with it, its level of inclusivity, and its degree of importance. As shown in Figure 7 majority of both groups agree and strongly agree with the VSU VMGO (22% & 71% for the faculty, staff, and other stakeholders, and 42.1% and 49.1% for the undergraduate students). In terms of inclusivity, most of both groups find the VSU VMGO inclusive, mainly because the VMGO was stated to encompass the welfare of all its stakeholders, especially the students (Figure 8). However, it is worth noting that a few still seemed indifferent. There were 18.5% on the side of the faculty and staff and other stakeholders, and 29.6% of the undergraduate students who were neutral. Meaning they may be open and confident on what would be approved by the university. In terms of importance, Figure 9 shows that almost all of the respondents of both groups found it very important – 91.1% for the faculty, staff, and other stakeholders, and 87.4% for the undergraduate students.

The answers of the respondents were an excellent sign that the VSU VMGO is honed, gearing towards what is best for the university and its stakeholders, and that it is generally very well understood.

Figure 7. Respondents' response if they agree of the VSU VMGO

Figure 8. Respondents' opinion of VSU VMGO inclusivity

Figure 9. Importance of VSU VMGO

4. CONCLUSION

The study was conducted to determine the level of awareness and acceptance of the VSU faculty and staff, other stakeholders, and the VSU undergraduate students to the VSU's vision, mission, goals, and objectives (VMGO). Since the conduct of the study was in the COVID 19 pandemic, the questionnaires in Google form were utilized. The responses to the questionnaires were voluntary. The questions on stakeholders' level of awareness and acceptance of VSU VMGO were formulated in Likert scale-based questions. Descriptive statistics were used in the analysis.

The results of the study revealed that most stakeholders are well aware of the VSU VMGO. They mostly sourced this information from the VSU official website, which is logical for online classes and activities in the pandemic. The newly crafted and improved VMGO was also agreed, accepted, and felt very important by the stakeholders. This is a very good sign that the VSU VMGO is well-understood. This is thereby honed towards what is best for the university and its stakeholders.

In terms of keeping the VMGO in mind through memorization, it is good to note that majority have partially and fully memorized it. Although, it was also noticed that a large fraction of faculty and staff and other stakeholders were not able to memorize the goals and objectives. Moreover, it was noted that undergraduate students were neutral of the goals and objectives, which could be explained by the results of Bulfa et al. (2017) study, revealing educational attainment as a significant factor. Most undergraduate student-respondents were still in their first year, and university activities were commonly done online.

To keep stakeholders informed, it is recommended to maintain the mode of dissemination and explore other strategic measures of information dissemination of the VMGO. Suggestions from other researchers of other institutions like translating VMGO into the local dialect, that is, Cebuano, Waray-Waray, or Filipino, could be explored to sustain its existence and relevance to the local, national, and international community (Balcorta et al., 2021).

Since this study was done during the COVID 19 pandemic, an intensive survey is recommended so that respondents not connected to the internet can also be reached. Respondents from other satellite campuses can also be included to increase the sample size. To further validate results, focus-group discussions can be done. A study on the VMGO impact on the students, community, and employee's work performance may be conducted as part of future studies.

5. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

6. INFORMED CONSENT

Informed consent was obtained from all respondents involved in the study.

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